

New development of the neutrosophic fuzzy soft set framework using several aggregation operator techniques

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Abstract. The soft set is a general mathematical technique for dealing with uncertainty. For this reason, the soft set theory has attracted a lot of attention from academics, particularly in the context of managing uncertainty in decision-making scenarios. However, since the membership degrees of the components that comprise the universe set in the theory are only stated with 0 or 1, it is difficult to precisely characterize the uncertainty. The interval valued Pythagorean neutrosophic soft set (IVPNSS) is an extension of the Pythagorean fuzzy soft set and interval valued neutrosophic soft set. Based on the aggregating method, we talk about aggregated operations for IVPNSS over a scoring function. to determine which choice is optimal. We use practical problems to ascertain how a buyer must decide which motorcycle to purchase. For instance, a car company produces ten various kinds of motorcycles, and a set of criteria includes things like fuel tank capacity, improved style, higher mileage, and durability. In the end, these algorithms were compared, and it was made obvious how they differed from earlier algorithms that had been suggested. To illustrate the comparison study, sensitivity analysis and the viability of our suggested technique are both carried out. Decision makers will find the results very helpful in effectively handling contradicting and unclear information.

Keywords: Soft set, neutrosophic fuzzy soft set, decision making, aggregation operator.

Abbreviations

DM	Decision making
AO	Aggregation operator
MD	Membership degree
NMD	Non membership degree
TD	Truth degree
ID	Indeterminacy degree
FD	False degree
FS	Fuzzy set
IFS	Intuitionistic fuzzy set
NS	Neutrosophic set
PFS	Pythagorean fuzzy set
IVPFS	Interval valued Pythagorean fuzzy set

1. Introduction

Every day, machine learning, collecting data, information and other techniques are applied in solving conflicts. One of the most difficult problem is demonstrating the effectiveness of basic planning. Mathematical theory enables the use of proper decision-making (DM) procedures. Since the DM idea evaluates and ranks many points of view according to their attributes, it may be beneficial to enterprises. MADM considers every feature and component to provide the optimal response. It used to be widely accepted that weights and attributes required to be expressed as distinct numerical values. several assessments and DM problems require the analysis of several factors and indications. Assessing and collecting data for evaluation indicators can help overcome assessment and DM problems. The complexities of real-world systems usually result in MADM difficulties that conceal evaluation specifics. Decision making (DM) challenges suggest how to find the best possible options. Hwang et al. [12] discussed strategies for multiple criterion decision making (MCDM). The matrix form of MCDM problem as

$$\Xi_{m \times n} = \begin{matrix} & \Xi_1 & \Xi_2 & \dots & \Xi_n \\ \Upsilon_1 & \left(\begin{matrix} \tau_{11} & \tau_{12} & \dots & \tau_{1n} \end{matrix} \right) \\ \Upsilon_2 & \left(\begin{matrix} \tau_{21} & \tau_{22} & \dots & \tau_{2n} \end{matrix} \right) \\ \vdots & \left(\begin{matrix} \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \end{matrix} \right) \\ \Upsilon_m & \left(\begin{matrix} \tau_{m1} & \tau_{m2} & \dots & \tau_{mn} \end{matrix} \right) \end{matrix}$$

where $\Upsilon_1, \Upsilon_2, \dots, \Upsilon_m$ are potential options from which decision makers must select; $\Xi_1, \Xi_2, \dots, \Xi_n$ are referred to as criteria and x_{ij} is the rating of Υ_i to Ξ_j . The interval valued fuzzy soft sets were examined by Xiao et al. in 2013 [25].

The truth and falsity values of Boolean logic are represented by the numbers one and zero, respectively. But Zadeh expanded on the concept of Boolean logic by introducing fuzzy logic.

In the majority of everyday problems, uncertainty is present everywhere. To deal with the uncertainties, the neutrosophic set (NSS) [21], interval valued FS [22], interval valued IFS [6], and PFS are suggested. The application of complex intuitionistic fuzzy DOMBI prioritized AOs was discussed by Wang et al. [24]. FS logic, which uses only MD to solve DM problems were introduced by Zadeh. An IFS logic first proposed by Atanassov by the condition that the sum of its MD and NMD values be less than or equal to one. While the sum of the MD and NMD values is greater than or equal to one, we may encounter problems while using DM. Yager defined the new concept of PFS logic, an extension of IFS, as the square sum of its MD and NMD, where the value is less than or equal to one. Indeterminacy is measured explicitly in NS, but MD, IND, and FD are independent. This assumption is critical in many applications, including information fusion, which combines data from several sensors. Broumi et al. [7] applied IVNS to DM problems using soft sets. Deli [9] utilized soft sets to define the IVNS. Broumi et al. [8] provides a definition for IVNS-based similarity assessments. Deli et al. introduced a similarity measure based on NS that uses soft sets [10]. Jansi et al. introduced a correlation measure for Pythagorean NSs [13].

Yager [26] presented PFSs and condition that square sum of the MD and NMD not exceed unity. Peng et al. [18] developed the fuzzy soft set to include Pythagorean fuzzy soft sets and discussed their practical applications. Recently, Ullah et al. [23] investigated the concept of complex PFSs and its potential applications in pattern detection. Akram et al. proposed bipolar fuzzy TOPSIS for GDM [5]. After 2019, Adeel and associates [3] discussed the m -polar fuzzy linguistic TOPSIS method for MCGDM. While Zhang and Xu proposed extending PFSs based on TOPSIS to MCDM [27], Peng et al. [19] established the concept of single valued NS based on MABAC and TOPSIS. Zulqarnain et al. [28] discussed the potential application of TOPSIS to interval valued intuitionistic fuzzy soft set (IVIFSS). He also discussed a new type of correlation coefficient under IVIFSS. The notion of FS with extension based on AO operators were discussed by Palanikumar et al. [15–17]. The NS and its extension were developed by multiple researchers [1, 2, 4, 11, 20].

1.1. *Current research gaps and the reasons behind our investigation:*

The Pythagorean fuzzy soft set and interval valued neutrosophic soft set are extended by the interval valued Pythagorean neutrosophic soft set (IVPNSS). We discuss aggregated operations for IVPNSS over a scoring function based on the aggregating approach. FSs and its extensions, including IFS, PFS and IVPNSS may enhanced the representation of uncertain information. However, they are subject to a distinct set of limitations. These two concepts have extensive implications. IVPNSS is a proposed framework for correlating a dependability index with a variety of data input from decision makers. As a result, IVPNSSs may determine the level of

certainty in the data collected while also communicating unclear information more precisely. Our primary goals and contributions are:

- (1) Additionally, IVPNSS can be applied in extremely unclear and troubling scenarios. Notably, this work is intended for proposed IVPNSSs.
- (2) The new score values for four methodologies for ranking IVPNSSs.
- (3) Our suggested methods for calculating score values are significantly more reliable and effective than the present methods. Our technique also examines the accuracy of current information.
- (4) Flowchart for applying DM problems using IVPNSSs.

The article is structured as follows: The introduction appears in Section 1. Section 2 includes a quick description of IVPNSS. Section 3 discusses MCGDM using IVPNSS and provides examples. Section 4 discusses the comparison of suggested and existing approaches. Section 5 discusses the sensitivity analysis, limitations, and advantages of our proposed technique. Section 6 summarizes our findings and suggests some possibilities for future investigation.

Figure 1 representation fuzzy set origin.

Figure 1 Flowchart representation based on fuzzy origin.

2. Preliminaries

In this section \mathcal{U} be a universe.

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Definition 2.1. Let \mathcal{D} be a IVPFS in \mathcal{U} as $\widehat{\mathcal{D}} = \left\{ b, \left\langle \widehat{\zeta_{\mathcal{D}}^{-}}(b), \widehat{\zeta_{\mathcal{D}}^{\downarrow}}(b) \right\rangle \mid b \in \mathcal{U} \right\}$ denotes the MG and NMG of \mathcal{D} respectively. Here $\widehat{\zeta_{\mathcal{D}}^{-}}$ and $\widehat{\zeta_{\mathcal{D}}^{\downarrow}}$ are belongs to \mathcal{U} into $\mathcal{D}[0, 1]$ and $0 \leq (\widehat{\zeta_{\mathcal{D}}^{-}}(b))^2 + (\widehat{\zeta_{\mathcal{D}}^{\downarrow}}(b))^2 \leq 1$ it is observed that $0 \leq (\zeta_{\mathcal{D}}^{-U}(b))^2 + (\zeta_{\mathcal{D}}^{\downarrow U}(b))^2 \leq 1$.

Definition 2.2. Let \mathcal{D} be a neutrosophic set (NS) in \mathcal{U} as $\mathcal{D} = \left\{ b, \langle \zeta_{\mathcal{D}}^{-}(b), \zeta_{\mathcal{D}}^{\downarrow}(b) \rangle \mid b \in \mathcal{U} \right\}$, where $\zeta_{\mathcal{D}}^{-}(b)$ and $\zeta_{\mathcal{D}}^{\downarrow}(b)$ are called MG and NMG of \mathcal{D} respectively. Here $\zeta_{\mathcal{D}}^{-}$ and $\zeta_{\mathcal{D}}^{\downarrow}$ are belongs to \mathcal{U} into $[0, 1]$ and $0 \leq (\zeta_{\mathcal{D}}^{-}(b))^3 + (\zeta_{\mathcal{D}}^{\downarrow}(b))^3 \leq 1$.

Definition 2.3. The IVNS \mathcal{D} in \mathcal{U} as $\widehat{\mathcal{D}} = \left\{ b, \left(\widehat{\psi_{\mathcal{D}}^{-}}(b), \widehat{\psi_{\mathcal{D}}^{\downarrow}}(b), \widehat{\psi_{\mathcal{D}}^{\downarrow}}(b) \right) \mid b \in \mathcal{U} \right\}$, where $\widehat{\psi_{\mathcal{D}}^{-}}(b)$, $\widehat{\psi_{\mathcal{D}}^{\downarrow}}(b)$ and $\widehat{\psi_{\mathcal{D}}^{\downarrow}}(b)$ represents the MG, IMG and NMG of \mathcal{D} respectively. Consider $\widehat{\psi_{\mathcal{D}}^{-}}, \widehat{\psi_{\mathcal{D}}^{\downarrow}} : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow D[0, 1], \widehat{\psi_{\mathcal{D}}^{\downarrow}} : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow D[0, 1]$ and $0 \leq (\widehat{\psi_{\mathcal{D}}^{-}}(b))^2 + (\widehat{\psi_{\mathcal{D}}^{\downarrow}}(b))^2 + (\widehat{\psi_{\mathcal{D}}^{\downarrow}}(b))^2 \leq 2$. Here $\widehat{\mathcal{D}}$ is called a interval valued Pythagorean neutrosophic number (IVPNN).

Definition 2.4. Let \mathcal{U} and E be the universe and set of parameter respectively. The pair $(\mathfrak{S}, \mathcal{D})$ or $\widehat{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathcal{D}}}$ is called a IVPNSS on \mathcal{U} if $\mathcal{D} \subseteq E$ and $\mathfrak{S} : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow IVPNS^{\mathcal{U}}$, where $IVPNS^{\mathcal{U}}$ is denote the set of all IVPNS subsets of \mathcal{U} . That is $\widehat{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathcal{D}}} = \left\{ \left(e, \left\{ \frac{b}{\left([\psi_{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathcal{D}}}^{TL}(b), \psi_{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathcal{D}}}^{TU}(b)], [\psi_{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathcal{D}}}^{IL}(b), \psi_{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathcal{D}}}^{IU}(b)], [\psi_{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathcal{D}}}^{FL}(b), \psi_{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathcal{D}}}^{FU}(b)] \right)} \right\} \right) : e \in \mathcal{D}, b \in \mathcal{U} \right\}$.

3. IVPNSS concept via MCGDM

Definition 3.1. The cardinal set of the IVPNSS $\widehat{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathcal{D}}}$ is denoted by $\widehat{c\mathfrak{S}_{\mathcal{D}}}$ and is defined as $\widehat{c\mathfrak{S}_{\mathcal{D}}} = \left\{ \frac{e}{\left(\widehat{\psi_{c\theta_{\mathcal{D}}}}(e), \widehat{\psi_{c\xi_{\mathcal{D}}}}(e), \widehat{\psi_{c\varphi_{\mathcal{D}}}}(e) \right)} : e \in E \right\}$, where $\widehat{\psi_{c\theta_{\mathcal{D}}}}, \widehat{\psi_{c\xi_{\mathcal{D}}}}$ and $\widehat{\psi_{c\varphi_{\mathcal{D}}}}$:

$E \rightarrow D[0, 1]$ are mapping respectively, where $\widehat{\psi_{c\theta_{\mathcal{D}}}}(e) = \frac{|\theta_{\mathcal{D}}(e)|}{|\mathcal{U}|}$, $\widehat{\psi_{c\xi_{\mathcal{D}}}}(e) = \frac{|\xi_{\mathcal{D}}(e)|}{|\mathcal{U}|}$ and $\widehat{\psi_{c\varphi_{\mathcal{D}}}}(e) = \frac{|\varphi_{\mathcal{D}}(e)|}{|\mathcal{U}|}$, where $|\theta_{\mathcal{D}}(e)|$, $|\xi_{\mathcal{D}}(e)|$ and $|\varphi_{\mathcal{D}}(e)|$ is the scalar cardinalities of the IVPNSSs $\widehat{\theta_{\mathcal{D}}}(e)$, $\widehat{\xi_{\mathcal{D}}}(e)$ and $\widehat{\varphi_{\mathcal{D}}}(e)$ respectively, and $|\mathcal{U}|$ represents cardinality of \mathcal{U} . The collection of all cardinal sets of \mathcal{U} is represented as $cIVPNS^{\mathcal{U}}$. If $\mathcal{D} \subseteq E = \{e_i : i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$, then $\widehat{c\mathfrak{S}_{\mathcal{D}}} \in cIVPNS^{\mathcal{U}}$, the matrix form as $\left(\widehat{p_{1j}}, \widehat{q_{1j}}, \widehat{r_{1j}} \right)_{1 \times n} = \left(\widehat{p_{11}}, \widehat{q_{11}}, \widehat{r_{11}} \right), \left(\widehat{p_{12}}, \widehat{q_{12}}, \widehat{r_{12}} \right), \dots, \left(\widehat{p_{1n}}, \widehat{q_{1n}}, \widehat{r_{1n}} \right)$, where $\left(\widehat{p_{1j}}, \widehat{q_{1j}}, \widehat{r_{1j}} \right) = \widehat{\mu_{c\mathfrak{S}_{\mathcal{D}}}}(e_j)$, for $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$. For our convenience, consider matrix form as $[(\widehat{p_{1j}}, \widehat{q_{1j}}, \widehat{r_{1j}})]_{1 \times n} = [(\widehat{p_{11}}, \widehat{q_{11}}, \widehat{r_{11}}), (\widehat{p_{12}}, \widehat{q_{12}}, \widehat{r_{12}}), \dots, (\widehat{p_{1n}}, \widehat{q_{1n}}, \widehat{r_{1n}})]$, where $(\widehat{p_{1j}}, \widehat{q_{1j}}, \widehat{r_{1j}}) = \widehat{\mu_{c\mathfrak{S}_{\mathcal{D}}}}(e_j)$, for $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Hence this matrix is called a cardinal matrix of $\widehat{c\mathfrak{S}_{\mathcal{D}}}$ of E .

Remark 3.2. If we write $\widehat{p_{ij}} = \widehat{\psi_{\mathfrak{D}}^{\uparrow}(e_j)(b_i)}$, $\widehat{q_{ij}} = \widehat{\psi_{\mathfrak{D}}^{\downarrow}(e_j)(b_i)}$ and $\widehat{r_{ij}} = \widehat{\psi_{\mathfrak{D}}^{\downarrow}(e_j)(b_i)}$, where $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ then the IVPNSS $\widehat{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}$ defined in matrix form: $\widehat{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}} = [(\widehat{p_{ij}}, \widehat{q_{ij}}, \widehat{r_{ij}})]_{m \times n}$. This matrix is called Pythagorean neutrosophic interval valued soft matrix (IVPNISM).

Definition 3.3. Let $\widehat{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}} \in IVPNS^{\mathcal{U}}$ and $\widehat{c\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}} \in cIVPNSS^{\mathcal{U}}$. The IVPNSS aggregation operator $IVPNSS_{agg} : cIVPNSS^{\mathcal{U}} \times IVPNS^{\mathcal{U}} \rightarrow IVPNSS(\mathcal{U}, E)$ is defined as

$$IVPNSS_{agg}(\widehat{c\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}, \widehat{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}) = \left\{ \frac{b}{\mu_{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}^*(b)} : b \in \mathcal{U} \right\} = \left\{ \frac{b}{\left(\widehat{\psi_{\theta_{\mathfrak{D}}}^{\uparrow}(b)}, \widehat{\psi_{\xi_{\mathfrak{D}}}^{\uparrow}(b)}, \widehat{\psi_{\varphi_{\mathfrak{D}}}^{\uparrow}(b)} \right)} : b \in \mathcal{U} \right\}.$$

This collection is called aggregate IVPNSS $\widehat{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}$. The truth $\widehat{\psi_{\theta_{\mathfrak{D}}}^{\uparrow}(b)} : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow D[0, 1]$ by $\widehat{\psi_{\theta_{\mathfrak{D}}}^{\uparrow}(b)} = \frac{1}{|E|} \sum_{e \in E} \left(\widehat{\psi_{c\theta_{\mathfrak{D}}}^{\uparrow}(e)}, \widehat{\psi_{\theta_{\mathfrak{D}}}^{\uparrow}(e)} \right) (b)$, indeterminacy $\widehat{\psi_{\xi_{\mathfrak{D}}}^{\uparrow}(b)} : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow D[0, 1]$ by $\widehat{\psi_{\xi_{\mathfrak{D}}}^{\uparrow}(b)} = \frac{1}{|E|} \sum_{e \in E} \left(\widehat{\psi_{c\xi_{\mathfrak{D}}}^{\uparrow}(e)}, \widehat{\psi_{\xi_{\mathfrak{D}}}^{\uparrow}(e)} \right) (b)$ and falsity $\widehat{\psi_{\varphi_{\mathfrak{D}}}^{\uparrow}(b)} : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow D[0, 1]$ by $\widehat{\psi_{\varphi_{\mathfrak{D}}}^{\uparrow}(b)} = \frac{1}{|E|} \sum_{e \in E} \left(\widehat{\psi_{c\varphi_{\mathfrak{D}}}^{\uparrow}(e)}, \widehat{\psi_{\varphi_{\mathfrak{D}}}^{\uparrow}(e)} \right) (b)$. The set $IVPNSS_{agg}(\widehat{c\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}, \widehat{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}})$ is expressed in matrix form as $\left[\left(\widehat{p_{i1}}, \widehat{q_{i1}}, \widehat{r_{i1}} \right) \right]_{m \times 1}$ where $\left[\left(\widehat{p_{i1}}, \widehat{q_{i1}}, \widehat{r_{i1}} \right) \right] = \left[\mu_{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}^*(b_i), \mu_{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}^*(b_i) \right]$, for $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$. This matrix is called IVPNSS aggregate matrix of $IVPNSS_{agg}(\widehat{c\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}, \widehat{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}})$ over \mathcal{U} .

Methods: Let $\widehat{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}$ be an IVPNSS. Suppose that $\widehat{M_{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}}, \widehat{M_{c\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}}, \widehat{M_{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}^*}$ are matrices of $\widehat{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}, \widehat{c\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}, \widehat{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}^*$ respectively, then $\widehat{M_{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}} \circ \widehat{M_{c\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}^{\uparrow}} = \widehat{M_{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}^*} \times |E|$, where $\widehat{M_{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}} \circ \widehat{M_{c\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}^{\uparrow}}$ is called a IVPNSSM-max min product and $\widehat{M_{c\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}^{\uparrow}}$ is the transpose of $\widehat{M_{c\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}}$.

We can make a MCGDM based on IVPNSS by the following algorithms:

Method-I

- Step 1:** Input IVPNSS $\widehat{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}$ over \mathcal{U} .
- Step 2:** Find the cardinal set $\widehat{c\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}$ of $\widehat{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}$.
- Step 3:** Obtain aggregate IVPNSS $\widehat{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}^*$ of $\widehat{\mathfrak{S}_{\mathfrak{D}}}$.
- Step 4:** Determine the score value $S_c(b) = \frac{(\psi_b^{2TL} - \psi_b^{2IU} - \psi_b^{2FU}) + (\psi_b^{2TU} - \psi_b^{2IL} - \psi_b^{2FL})}{2}$, $-1 \leq S_c(b) \leq 1$ and $b \in \mathcal{U}$.
- Step 5:** Output for the best alternative by $S_c(b)$ is maximum.

Example 3.4. Assume that a car manufacturer manufactures ten distinct kinds of motorcycles $\mathcal{U} = \{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_{10}\}$. Let $E = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_5\}$ stand for each of the following: fuel tank capacity, better style, better pricing, greater mileage, and durability. Assuming that the buyer must choose which motorcycle to buy, each motorcycle is assessed according to a subset of parameters $\mathfrak{D} = \{e_1, e_3, e_5\} \subseteq E$. Here is how we invoke algorithm-I.

Step-1: Form IVPNSS $\widehat{\mathfrak{S}}_{\mathfrak{D}}$ of \mathcal{U} as below:

$$\widehat{\mathfrak{S}}_{\mathfrak{D}} = \left\{ \left(e_1, \left\{ \frac{\alpha_1}{[0.6,0.65],[0.65,0.7],[0.5,0.52]}, \frac{\alpha_2}{[0.65,0.7],[0.5,0.55],[0.6,0.63]}, \frac{\alpha_5}{[0.9,0.95],[0.1,0.13],[0.45,0.5]}, \right. \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \frac{\alpha_7}{[0.17,0.2],[0.73,0.75],[0.68,0.7]}, \frac{\alpha_{10}}{[0.17,0.25],[0.75,0.8],[0.65,0.68]} \right\} \right), \\ \left(e_3, \left\{ \frac{\alpha_3}{[0.58,0.65],[0.65,0.7],[0.5,0.53]}, \frac{\alpha_4}{[0.2,0.5],[0.75,0.78],[0.65,0.67]}, \frac{\alpha_6}{[0.5,0.55],[0.7,0.8],[0.75,0.78]}, \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \frac{\alpha_8}{[0.23,0.35],[0.56,0.58],[0.8,0.83]}, \frac{\alpha_9}{[0.6,0.65],[0.65,0.68],[0.48,0.5]} \right\} \right), \\ \left(e_5, \left\{ \frac{\alpha_1}{[0.24,0.3],[0.77,0.78],[0.6,0.62]}, \frac{\alpha_2}{[0.8,0.85],[0.1,0.12],[0.6,0.64]}, \frac{\alpha_3}{[0.32,0.35],[0.7,0.72],[0.65,0.67]}, \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \frac{\alpha_4}{[0.33,0.4],[0.9,0.95],[0.3,0.35]}, \frac{\alpha_5}{[0.26,0.5],[0.7,0.72],[0.7,0.75]}, \frac{\alpha_8}{[0.85,0.9],[0.15,0.2],[0.6,0.62]} \right\} \right) \Big\}.$$

Step-2: The cardinal set of $\widehat{\mathfrak{S}}_{\mathfrak{D}}$ can be written as $c\widehat{\mathfrak{S}}_{\mathfrak{D}} = \left\{ \frac{e_1}{([0.249,0.275],[0.273,0.293],[0.288,0.303])}, \frac{e_3}{([0.211,0.27],[0.331,0.354],[0.318,0.331])}, \frac{e_5}{([0.28,0.33],[0.332,0.349],[0.345,0.365])} \right\}.$

Step-3: The aggregate IVPNSS $\widehat{\mathfrak{S}}_{\mathfrak{D}}^*$ of $\widehat{\mathfrak{S}}_{\mathfrak{D}}$ is $M_{\widehat{\mathfrak{S}}_{\mathfrak{D}}^*} = \frac{M_{\widehat{\mathfrak{S}}_{\mathfrak{D}}} \circ M_{c\widehat{\mathfrak{S}}_{\mathfrak{D}}}^T}{|E|}$

$$= \frac{1}{5} \left\{ \begin{matrix} \begin{bmatrix} [0.6, 0.65] & 0 & 0 & 0 & [0.24, 0.3] \\ [0.65, 0.7] & 0 & 0 & 0 & [0.8, 0.85] \\ 0 & 0 & [0.58, 0.65] & 0 & [0.32, 0.35] \\ 0 & 0 & [0.2, 0.5] & 0 & [0.33, 0.4] \\ [0.9, 0.95] & 0 & 0 & 0 & [0.26, 0.5] \\ 0 & 0 & [0.5, 0.55] & 0 & 0 \\ [0.17, 0.2] & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & [0.23, 0.35] & 0 & [0.85, 0.9] \\ 0 & 0 & [0.6, 0.65] & 0 & 0 \\ [0.17, 0.25] & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} & \begin{bmatrix} [0.249, 0.275] \\ 0 \\ [0.211, 0.27] \\ 0 \\ [0.28, 0.33] \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix} \right\},$$

$$\begin{matrix} \begin{bmatrix} [0.65, 0.7] & 0 & 0 & 0 & [0.77, 0.78] \\ [0.5, 0.55] & 0 & 0 & 0 & [0.1, 0.12] \\ 0 & 0 & [0.65, 0.7] & 0 & [0.7, 0.72] \\ 0 & 0 & [0.75, 0.78] & 0 & [0.9, 0.95] \\ [0.1, 0.13] & 0 & 0 & 0 & [0.7, 0.72] \\ 0 & 0 & [0.7, 0.8] & 0 & 0 \\ [0.73, 0.75] & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & [0.56, 0.58] & 0 & [0.15, 0.2] \\ 0 & 0 & [0.65, 0.68] & 0 & 0 \\ [0.75, 0.8] & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} & \begin{bmatrix} [0.273, 0.293] \\ 0 \\ [0.331, 0.354] \\ 0 \\ [0.332, 0.349] \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix},$$

$$\left[\begin{array}{cccc} [0.5, 0.52] & 0 & 0 & 0 & [0.6, 0.62] \\ [0.6, 0.63] & 0 & 0 & 0 & [0.6, 0.64] \\ 0 & 0 & [0.5, 0.53] & 0 & [0.65, 0.67] \\ 0 & 0 & [0.65, 0.67] & 0 & [0.3, 0.35] \\ [0.45, 0.5] & 0 & 0 & 0 & [0.7, 0.75] \\ 0 & 0 & [0.75, 0.78] & 0 & 0 \\ [0.68, 0.7] & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & [0.8, 0.83] & 0 & [0.6, 0.62] \\ 0 & 0 & [0.48, 0.5] & 0 & 0 \\ [0.65, 0.68] & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{array} \right] \left. \vphantom{\begin{array}{c} [0.288, 0.303] \\ 0 \\ [0.318, 0.331] \\ 0 \\ [0.345, 0.365] \end{array}} \right\}$$

$$= \left[\begin{array}{l} [0.0498, 0.06], [0.0664, 0.0698], [0.069, 0.073] \\ [0.056, 0.066], [0.0546, 0.0586], [0.069, 0.073] \\ [0.056, 0.066], [0.0664, 0.0708], [0.069, 0.073] \\ [0.056, 0.066], [0.0664, 0.0708], [0.0636, 0.07] \\ [0.052, 0.066], [0.0664, 0.0698], [0.069, 0.073] \\ [0.0422, 0.054], [0.0662, 0.0708], [0.0636, 0.0662] \\ [0.034, 0.04], [0.0546, 0.0586], [0.0576, 0.0606] \\ [0.056, 0.066], [0.0662, 0.0708], [0.069, 0.073] \\ [0.0422, 0.054], [0.0662, 0.0708], [0.0636, 0.0662] \\ [0.034, 0.04], [0.0546, 0.0586], [0.0576, 0.0606] \end{array} \right]$$

Hence, $\widehat{\mathfrak{S}}_{\mathfrak{D}}^* = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{\alpha_1}{([0.0498, 0.06], [0.0664, 0.0698], [0.069, 0.073])}, \frac{\alpha_2}{([0.056, 0.066], [0.0546, 0.0586], [0.069, 0.073])}, \\ \frac{\alpha_3}{([0.056, 0.066], [0.0664, 0.0708], [0.069, 0.073])}, \frac{\alpha_4}{([0.056, 0.066], [0.0664, 0.0708], [0.0636, 0.07])}, \\ \frac{\alpha_5}{([0.052, 0.066], [0.0664, 0.0698], [0.069, 0.073])}, \frac{\alpha_6}{([0.0422, 0.054], [0.0662, 0.0708], [0.0636, 0.0662])}, \\ \frac{\alpha_7}{([0.034, 0.04], [0.0546, 0.0586], [0.0576, 0.0606])}, \frac{\alpha_8}{([0.056, 0.066], [0.0662, 0.0708], [0.069, 0.073])}, \\ \frac{\alpha_9}{([0.0422, 0.054], [0.0662, 0.0708], [0.0636, 0.0662])}, \frac{\alpha_{10}}{([0.034, 0.04], [0.0546, 0.0586], [0.0576, 0.0606])} \end{array} \right\}.$

Step-4: The values of the score function $S_c(\alpha_i)$ as follows.

α_i	α_1	α_2	α_3	α_4	α_5
$S_c(\alpha_i)$	-0.00665	-0.00451	-0.00601	-0.00544	-0.00616
α_i	α_6	α_7	α_8	α_9	α_{10}
$S_c(\alpha_i)$	-0.00656	-0.00532	-0.006	-0.00656	-0.00487

Step 5: Here $\max_i S_c(\alpha_i) = -0.00451$.

Method-2

Step-1: Input IVPNSS matrix.

Step-2: (Case-I) When weights are equal, find the choice matrix for the IVPNSS matrix as truth, indeterminacy, and falsity.

(Case-II) When weights are not equal, find the choice matrix for the IVPNSS matrix as truth, indeterminacy, and falsehood.

Step-3: Compute score value $S_c(b) = \frac{(\psi_b^{2TL} - \psi_b^{2IU} - \psi_b^{2FU}) + (\psi_b^{2TU} - \psi_b^{2IL} - \psi_b^{2FL})}{2}$, $-1 \leq S_c(b) \leq 1$.

Step-4: The output of $S_c(b)$ for the optimal option is at its highest.

Case-I: Let $\widehat{\mathcal{D}} = (\widehat{\psi_{ij}^T}, \widehat{\psi_{ij}^I}, \widehat{\psi_{ij}^F}) \in IVPNSSM_{m \times n}$. Then choice matrix of IVPNSSM \mathcal{D} is given by $\widehat{\mathcal{C}}(\mathcal{D}) = \left[\left(\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (\widehat{\psi_{ij}^T})^2}{n}, \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (\widehat{\psi_{ij}^I})^2}{n}, \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (\widehat{\psi_{ij}^F})^2}{n} \right) \right]_{m \times 1}$, $\forall i$ when weights are equal.

By Example 3.4,

$$\widehat{\mathcal{C}}(\mathcal{D}) = \begin{bmatrix} [0.0835, 0.1025], [0.2031, 0.2197], [0.122, 0.131] \\ [0.2125, 0.2425], [0.052, 0.0634], [0.144, 0.1613] \\ [0.0878, 0.109], [0.1825, 0.2017], [0.1345, 0.146] \\ [0.0298, 0.082], [0.2745, 0.3022], [0.1025, 0.1143] \\ [0.1755, 0.2305], [0.1, 0.1071], [0.1385, 0.1625] \\ [0.05, 0.0605], [0.098, 0.128], [0.1125, 0.1217] \\ [0.0058, 0.008], [0.1066, 0.1125], [0.0925, 0.098] \\ [0.1551, 0.1865], [0.0672, 0.0753], [0.2, 0.2147] \\ [0.072, 0.0845], [0.0845, 0.0925], [0.0461, 0.05] \\ [0.0058, 0.0125], [0.1125, 0.128], [0.0845, 0.0925] \end{bmatrix}$$

The values of the score function $S_c(\alpha_i)$ are follows.

α_i	α_1	α_2	α_3	α_4	α_5
$S_c(\alpha_i)$	-0.05203	0.02524	-0.0469	-0.09131	0.00844
α_i	α_6	α_7	α_8	α_9	α_{10}
$S_c(\alpha_i)$	-0.02365	-0.02104	-0.01872	-0.004	-0.02227

Case-II: Let $\widehat{\mathcal{D}} = (\widehat{\psi_{ij}^T}, \widehat{\psi_{ij}^I}, \widehat{\psi_{ij}^F}) \in IVPNSSM_{m \times n}$. Then weighted choice matrix of IVPNSSM \mathcal{D} ($\widehat{w}_j > 0$, weights are unequal) is given by $\widehat{\mathcal{C}}_w(\mathcal{D}) = \left[\left(\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \widehat{w}_j (\widehat{\psi_{ij}^T})^2}{\sum \widehat{w}_j}, \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \widehat{w}_j (\widehat{\psi_{ij}^I})^2}{\sum \widehat{w}_j}, \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \widehat{w}_j (\widehat{\psi_{ij}^F})^2}{\sum \widehat{w}_j} \right) \right]_{m \times 1}$, $\forall i$.

Weights $(\widehat{w}_j) = \{[0.16, 0.165], [0.14, 0.145], [0.18, 0.19], [0.17, 0.175], [0.15, 0.155]\}$. By Example 3.4,

$$\widehat{\mathcal{C}}_w(\mathcal{D}) = \begin{bmatrix} [0.0798, 0.1046], [0.1886, 0.2189], [0.1133, 0.1302] \\ [0.1971, 0.241], [0.05, 0.0652], [0.1345, 0.1612] \\ [0.0915, 0.1241], [0.1802, 0.2168], [0.1306, 0.1537] \\ [0.0284, 0.0904], [0.2684, 0.3194], [0.1079, 0.1303] \\ [0.1684, 0.2346], [0.0905, 0.1039], [0.1276, 0.1605] \\ [0.0542, 0.0718], [0.1063, 0.152], [0.122, 0.1445] \\ [0.0056, 0.0083], [0.1027, 0.116], [0.0891, 0.1011] \\ [0.142, 0.186], [0.0721, 0.0876], [0.2039, 0.2381] \\ [0.0781, 0.1003], [0.0916, 0.1098], [0.05, 0.0594] \\ [0.0056, 0.0129], [0.1084, 0.132], [0.0814, 0.0954] \end{bmatrix}$$

The scoring function $S_c(\alpha_i)$ has the following values.

α_i	α_1	α_2	α_3	α_4	α_5
$S_c(\alpha_i)$	-0.04799	0.02307	-0.04819	-0.09684	0.01117
α_i	α_6	α_7	α_8	α_9	α_{10}
$S_c(\alpha_i)$	-0.03103	-0.02104	-0.02817	-0.00516	-0.02236

Method-3

Step-1: Input aggregated IVPNSS weighted

averaging (IVPNWA) numbers u_i by $\widehat{\mathcal{C}}(\mathcal{D}) = \left(\sum_{j=1}^n \widehat{w}_j \widehat{\psi}_{ij}^{\uparrow}, \sum_{j=1}^n \widehat{w}_j \widehat{\psi}_{ij}^{\downarrow}, \sum_{j=1}^n \widehat{w}_j \widehat{\psi}_{ij} \right)$.

Step-2: Determine the score function $S_c(b) = \frac{(\psi_b^{2TL} - \psi_b^{2IU} - \psi_b^{2FU}) + (\psi_b^{2TU} - \psi_b^{2IL} - \psi_b^{2FL})}{2}$.

Step-3: The output of $S_c(b)$ for the optimal option is at its highest.

Weights $(\widehat{w}_j) = \{[0.16, 0.165], [0.14, 0.145], [0.18, 0.19], [0.17, 0.175], [0.15, 0.155]\}$.
By Example 3.4,

$$\widehat{\mathcal{C}}(\mathcal{D}) = \begin{bmatrix} [0.132, 0.1538], [0.2195, 0.2364], [0.17, 0.1819] \\ [0.224, 0.2473], [0.095, 0.1094], [0.186, 0.2032] \\ [0.1524, 0.1778], [0.222, 0.2446], [0.1875, 0.2046] \\ [0.0855, 0.157], [0.27, 0.2955], [0.162, 0.1816] \\ [0.183, 0.2343], [0.121, 0.1331], [0.177, 0.1988] \\ [0.09, 0.1045], [0.126, 0.152], [0.135, 0.1482] \\ [0.0272, 0.033], [0.1168, 0.1238], [0.1088, 0.1155] \\ [0.1689, 0.206], [0.1233, 0.1412], [0.234, 0.2538] \\ [0.108, 0.1235], [0.117, 0.1292], [0.0864, 0.095] \\ [0.0272, 0.0413], [0.12, 0.132], [0.104, 0.1122] \end{bmatrix}$$

The values of the score function $S_c(\alpha_i)$ are as follows.

α_i	α_1	α_2	α_3	α_4	α_5
$S_c(\alpha_i)$	-0.06249	0.00723	-0.06564	-0.09372	-0.00741
α_i	α_6	α_7	α_8	α_9	α_{10}
$S_c(\alpha_i)$	-0.03007	-0.02615	-0.04167	-0.00998	-0.02639

4. Comparison and effectiveness

It is impossible to overestimate the importance of score values in the MCGDM process. On the other hand, MCGDM research has been extremely limited. In these studies, score values have been used as selection criterion for alternatives like IVNSs, NSs, and vague sets. In order to determine whether the suggested DM methodology can be applied in practical situations, we intend to investigate other techniques for calculating score values in this study. Palanikumar et al. [17] discussed the concept of spherical Fermatean IVFSS based on MCGDM. Every computation has been done, so we can discuss the outcome. Considering methods 1, 2, and 3, the computations presented can be as follows:

<i>Methods(proposed)</i>	<i>Ranking of alternatives</i>	<i>Optimal</i>
<i>Method – 1</i>	$\alpha_1 \leq \alpha_6 = \alpha_9 \leq \alpha_5 \leq \alpha_3 \leq \alpha_8 \leq \alpha_4 \leq \alpha_7 \leq \alpha_{10} \leq \alpha_2$	α_2
<i>Method – 2 Case – (i)</i>	$\alpha_4 \leq \alpha_1 \leq \alpha_3 \leq \alpha_6 \leq \alpha_{10} \leq \alpha_7 \leq \alpha_8 \leq \alpha_9 \leq \alpha_5 \leq \alpha_2$	α_2
<i>Method – 2 Case – (ii)</i>	$\alpha_4 \leq \alpha_3 \leq \alpha_1 \leq \alpha_6 \leq \alpha_8 \leq \alpha_{10} \leq \alpha_7 \leq \alpha_9 \leq \alpha_5 \leq \alpha_2$	α_2
<i>Method – 3</i>	$\alpha_4 \leq \alpha_3 \leq \alpha_1 \leq \alpha_8 \leq \alpha_6 \leq \alpha_{10} \leq \alpha_7 \leq \alpha_9 \leq \alpha_5 \leq \alpha_2$	α_2

<i>Methods(palanikumar, 2022)</i>	<i>Ranking of alternatives</i>	<i>Optimal</i>
<i>Method – 1</i>	$\alpha_8 \leq \alpha_5 \leq \alpha_6 \leq \alpha_7 \leq \alpha_{10} \leq \alpha_9 \leq \alpha_4 \leq \alpha_1 \leq \alpha_3 \leq \alpha_2$	α_2
<i>Method – 2 Case – (i)</i>	$\alpha_4 \leq \alpha_1 \leq \alpha_3 \leq \alpha_9 \leq \alpha_8 \leq \alpha_7 \leq \alpha_6 \leq \alpha_{10} \leq \alpha_5 \leq \alpha_2$	α_2
<i>Method – 2 Case – (ii)</i>	$\alpha_4 \leq \alpha_1 \leq \alpha_3 \leq \alpha_7 \leq \alpha_{10} \leq \alpha_6 \leq \alpha_8 \leq \alpha_9 \leq \alpha_5 \leq \alpha_2$	α_2
<i>Method – 3</i>	$\alpha_4 \leq \alpha_1 \leq \alpha_3 \leq \alpha_8 \leq \alpha_7 \leq \alpha_{10} \leq \alpha_5 \leq \alpha_6 \leq \alpha_9 \leq \alpha_2$	α_2

Figure 2 representation method-1 alternative ranking.

Figure 2 Method-1 alternative ranking.

Figure 3 representation method-2 case-(i) alternative ranking.

Figure 4 representation method-2 case-(ii) alternative ranking.

Figure 5 representation method-3 alternative ranking.

Figure 3 Method-2 case-(i) alternative ranking.

Figure 4 Method-2 case-(ii) alternative ranking.

Figure 5 Method-3 alternative ranking.

The above research shows that α_2 is the best alternative for the decision maker. The suggested method can solve the DM problem using IVPNSS data. Moreover, a more precise method is produced by highlighting the different ranks among the choices. It has been observed that the second motorcycle is the best choice. Finally, the following factors influence the customer decision to buy the second motorcycle. Therefore, we proposed method can be very beneficial in DM. For every process, the best results with the highest value were obtained. The proposed aggregation processes were tested using available tools to demonstrate their superiority and validity. Compared to the existing procedure, the proposed AO has higher accuracy and reliability.

5. Sensitivity Analysis

The earlier technique is advantageous since it considers the links between the various attributes. Thus, the proposed technique yields superior outcomes. Palanikumar et al. [17] suggests that this method is more effective. This study calculated the IVPFNSN score values. We developed a novel concept for IVPFNSN score values. These numbers are presented in a basic mathematical manner that allows for practical computations. As a result, a numerical representation was generated to demonstrate the superiority of the scoring values. A real world application highlights the significance of score values. We suggested a novel method for determining the best solution to the MCGDM problem.

- (1) The fuel tank capacity is the largest among the other motorcycles.
- (2) The most fashionable motorcycle available.
- (3) It is thought to have the best item pricing among the other motorcycles.
- (4) The customers expectations are considered to be fulfilled by more mileage.
- (5) Superior than other motorcycles in terms of durability and strength.

5.1. Limitations

Distance is an important factor to the choosing the best options. In the end, the most beneficial approach yielded the best results. Current methods were used to assess the superiority and validity of the proposed aggregating techniques. The proposed AOs outperform the current approaches in terms of accuracy and reliability. This approach is effective because it evaluates the relationships between the various qualities. As a result, the suggested approach yielded superior ranking results. We can see from the given data that our method produced ranking results that were identical to those of the current aggregating strategy used by palanikumar et al. [17]. Consequently, a numerical example showed that the score values could be improved through the addition of both of these variables. The practical use of score values is illustrated with a real-world example. We suggest applying these techniques in order to solve the MCGDM problem as effectively as possible. This example facilitates comparison by highlighting a large number of options and alternatives depending on a specific set of attributes.

5.2. Advantages

This article outlines the recommended concept's benefits and advantages. One of the primary advantages of this strategy is that it enables multiple specialists to assess DM operations objectively and subjectively. A variety of options and possibilities that depends on the decision-makers possessing an ideal set of attributes will be provided as an example to help in the evaluation of the available options. The weighted approach generated by the model is

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the key component of this process. Decision makers can use a weighted technique that accepts score values to compare their selections or alternatives to preferences. The fundamental purpose of this strategy is to solve a greater range of complex problems. Along with the validity of the recommended technique and its general adaptability to handle a wide range of inputs and outputs, the impact of score functions, analysis, superiority, and a comparison of the proposed methodology to existing methodologies are all investigated.

6. Conclusion

This study introduces new weighted operators with a wide range of features, including scores. We used a variety of popular metrics to describe the weighted vector. Numerous criteria for aggregating operators have been examined. This paper focuses on the NSSS extension, which is based on MCGDM problems usually found in DM domains. After that, individuals may continue to make appropriate decisions. Decision-makers may select criteria for reaching a judgment that is consistent with the desired outcome. There are various practical uses for score values in data processing. Our goal was to make sure that the recommended method was both realistic and situational. Because ideas can be applied to real-world problems, they require a great amount of effort to develop. This concepts provided will be useful to future researchers. We use aggregation operations to solve MCGDM problems with known attribute weights.

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References

1. Abdallah Shihadeh, Khaled Ahmad Mohammad Matarneh, Raed Hatamleh, Randa Bashir Yousef Hijazeen, Mowafaq Omar Al-Qadri, Abdallah Al-Husban, An Example of Two-Fold Fuzzy Algebras Based On Neutrosophic Real Numbers, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 67,(2024), 169-178.
2. Abubaker, Ahmad A, Hatamleh, Raed, Matarneh, Khaled, Al-Husban, Abdallah, On the Numerica Solutions for Some Neutrosophic Singular Boundary Value Problems by Using (LPM) Polynomials, *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*,25(2), (2024), 197-205.
3. A. Adeel, M. Akram and A.N.A. Koam, Group decision-making based on m-polar fuzzy linguistic TOPSIS method, *Symmetry* 11(735) (2019), 1-20.
4. A., Ahmad. , Hatamleh, Raed. , Matarneh, Khaled. , Al-Husban, Abdallah. On the Irreversible k-Threshold Conversion Number for Some Graph Products and Neutrosophic Graphs. (2025). *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, 25(2), (2025), 183-196.
5. M. Akram and M. Arshad, A novel trapezoidal bipolar fuzzy TOPSIS method for group decision making, *Group Decision and Negotiation* (2018).
6. Atanassov, K. & Gargov, G. Interval valued intuitionistic fuzzy sets, *Fuzzy Sets and Systems*, 31 (1989), 343349.

Ahmad A. Abubaker, Abdallah Al-Husban, Murugan Palanikumar, R. Uma, New development of the neutrosophic fuzzy soft set framework using several aggregation operator techniques

7. Broumi, S., Sahin, R. & Smarandache, F. Generalized interval neutrosophic soft set and its decision making problem, *Journal of New Results in Science*, 7, (2014), 2947.
8. Broumi, S., Deli, I. & Smarandache, F. Distance and similarity measures of interval neutrosophic soft sets, In *Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Information Fusion*, Salamanca, Spain, (2014), 7996.
9. Deli, I. Interval valued neutrosophic soft sets and its decision making, *International Journal of Machine Learning and Cybernetics*, 8(2), (2017), 665676.
10. Deli, I., Eraslan, S. & Cagman, N. Interval valued neutrosophic soft sets and their decision making based on similarity measure, *Neural Computing and Applications*, 29(1), (2018), 187203.
11. Hatamleh, R., Al-Husban, A., Zubair, S. A. M., Elamin, M., Saeed, M. M., Abdolmaleki, E & Khattak, A. M. AI-Assisted Wearable Devices for Promoting Human Health and Strength Using Complex Interval-Valued Picture Fuzzy Soft Relations. *European Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, 18(1), (2025), 5523-5523.
12. C.L. Hwang, K. Yoon, *Multiple Attributes Decision Making Methods and Applications*, Springer, Berlin Heidelberg, 1981.
13. Jansi, R., Mohana, K. & Smarandache, F. Correlation Measure for Pythagorean Neutrosophic Sets with T and F as Dependent Neutrosophic Components, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 30, (2019), 202-212.
14. M. Palanikumar, N. Kausar, H. Garg, A. Iampan, S. Kadry, M. Sharaf, Medical robotic engineering selection based on square root neutrosophic normal interval-valued sets and their aggregated operators, *AIMS Mathematics*, 8(8), (2023), 17402–17432.
15. M. Palanikumar, K. Arulmozhi, MCGDM based on TOPSIS and VIKOR using Pythagorean neutrosophic soft with aggregation operators, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, (2022), 538–555.
16. M. Palanikumar, K. Arulmozhi, A. Iampan, Multi criteria group decision making based on VIKOR and TOPSIS methods for Fermatean fuzzy soft with aggregation operators, *ICIC Express Letters* 16 (10), (2022), 1129–1138.
17. M. Palanikumar and A. Iampan, Spherical Fermatean interval valued fuzzy soft set based on multi criteria group decision-making, *International Journal of Innovative Computing, Information and Control*, 18(2), 607619, (2022).
18. X.D. Peng, Y. Yang, J.P. Song, Pythagorean fuzzy soft set and its application, *Computer Engineering*, 41(7), (2015), 224-229.
19. X.D. Peng and J. Dai, Approaches to single-valued neutrosophic MADM based on MABAC, TOPSIS and new similarity measure with score function, *Neural Computing and Applications*, 29(10), (2018), 939-954.
20. Shihadeh, A., Matarneh, K. A. M., Hatamleh, R., Al-Qadri, M. O., & Al-Husban, A., On The Two-Fold Fuzzy n -Refined Neutrosophic Rings, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 68, (2024), 8-25.
21. Smarandache, F. A unifying field in logics, *Neutrosophy neutrosophic probability, set and logic*, American Research Press, Rehoboth, (1999).
22. Turksen, I. Interval valued fuzzy sets based on normal forms, *Fuzzy Sets and Systems*, 20, (1986), 191210.
23. K. Ullah, T. Mahmood, Z. Ali and N. Jan, On some distance measures of complex Pythagorean fuzzy sets and their applications in pattern recognition, *Complex and Intelligent Systems*, 1-13, (2019).
24. Wang, P., Zhu, B., Yu, Y., Ali, Z. & Almohsen, B. Complex intuitionistic fuzzy DOMBI prioritized aggregation operators and their application for resilient green supplier selection, *Facta Universitatis, Series: Mechanical Engineering*, 21(3), (2023), 339-357.
25. Z. Xiao, W.J. Chen, and L.L. Li, A method based on interval-valued fuzzy soft set for multi attribute group decision making problems under uncertain environment, *Knowledge and Information Systems*, 34, (2013), 653-669.
26. R.R. Yager, Pythagorean membership grades in multi criteria decision making, *IEEE Trans. Fuzzy Systems*, 22, (2014), 958-965.

Ahmad A. Abubaker, Abdallah Al-Husban, Murugan Palanikumar, R. Uma, New development of the neutrosophic fuzzy soft set framework using several aggregation operator techniques

27. X. Zhang and Z. Xu, Extension of TOPSIS to multiple criteria decision making with Pythagorean fuzzy sets, *International Journal of Intelligent Systems*, 29, (2014), 1061-1078.
28. R.M. Zulqarnain , Xiao Long Xin , Muhammad Saqlain and Waseem Asghar Khan, TOPSIS Method Based on the Correlation Coefficient of Interval-Valued Intuitionistic Fuzzy Soft Sets and Aggregation Operators with Their Alication in Decision-Making, *Journal of Mathematics*, 2021, 1-16.

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